

Long-Term Performance of Segmented Benthic Microbial Fuel Cells

Y. Meriah Arias-Thode, Lewis Hsu, Jeff A. Kagan, and D.
Bart Chadwick
Environmental Sciences
Space and Naval Warfare Systems Center-Pacific
San Diego, United States
meriah.ariasthode@navy.mil

Abstract— Benthic microbial fuel cells (BMFCs) are a class of bioelectrochemical systems (BESs) that are an emerging technology under development for applications of persistent ocean monitoring. BMFCs function via anaerobic bacteria metabolizing organic matter in sediment and providing electrons to buried anodes. These anodes are electrically connected via an external circuit to an aerobic cathode positioned in the water column. Previous projects by this same group involved large-scale deployments that demonstrated deployment of BMFC systems via a boat-towed sled. These long carpet like anodes (termed “Magic Carpet”) have been shown to generate power densities of 5-10 mW m⁻² in systems ranging from 10 - 40 m² systems. A major challenge in the field remains scaling up these systems to generate practical levels of power. This paper evaluates two iterations of segmented 20 m² Magic Carpet BMFC systems and compares their long-term performance.

Keywords—BMFC; MFC; SMFC; Scale-up; Energy harvester; Power source; Magic Carpet; San Diego Bay; Carbon cloth

I. INTRODUCTION

In the marine environment, microbial fuel cells, termed either benthic or bioelectrochemical systems (BESs), have been developed to generate power via anodic bacteria in the ocean sediment. These fuel cells capitalize on microbial activity to catalyze these reactions, eliminating the cost and complexity of specialized catalysts used in traditional chemical fuel cells [1]. Anodic bacteria in BESs transfer electrons to electrodes in the sediment. These electrons are then used to reduce oxygen at the cathode, producing electrical energy. BESs can provide an inexpensive means for providing long-duration power for low-power sensors useful for Navy needs [2].

Benthic microbial fuel cell (BMFC) field deployments in 2008 demonstrated the ability to power oceanographic equipment [2,3,4]. Since then, there have been efforts to improve BMFC power output [5,6] addition of carbon sources [6] and ease of deployment [7]. Some key considerations for power output identified during those experiments included choice of electrode materials [8,9], the choice of wire materials for current collectors, and the influence of site-specific sediment quality [10]. This paper addresses the longevity of power production in field deployments. This knowledge is necessary for use of benthic microbial fuel cell as long-term underwater power sources.

A major challenge in the field remains scaling up these systems to generate practical levels of power. The largest system previously deployed had 10m² anodes and obtained persistent power levels of about 100mW [7]. While power levels of 100 mW are adequate for some low-power systems, increasing these levels to 500-1000 mW while remaining practically deployable would significantly increase the range of applications for these systems. Therefore, continued development toward large scale BMFC systems is necessary to provide practical power to undersea devices. This paper evaluates two iterations of segmented 20 m² Magic Carpet BMFC systems and compares their long-term performance.

Both systems described in this paper were based on the large-scale Magic Carpet BMFC architecture and deployed using a towed sled device as previously described [11]. The first iteration Magic Carpet was an anode cloth (10m) rolled up into a plow blade on a towed sled and unfurled on the seafloor bottom. The sled was lowered off of a boat and the carbon fiber cloth anode becomes buried as the boat pulls the sled. The current (2nd) Magic Carpet system effectively buries two 1m x 10m anode arrays at depths of approximately 10 cm and 20 cm; projected surface area is approximately 40 m². In both systems, the anode and cathode arrays were connected to a custom electronics pod that housed the energy harvesting package to maintain operating potential, monitor performance, and power management electronics, as well connect to the cathode assemblage in contact with the overlying surface water. This paper describes two systems different systems that are 20 m² total of anode material. Magic Carpet A (MCA) is a 20 segmented system with one channel; so all are electrically connected. Magic Carpet B (MCB) is a 20 segmented system with 20 individual harvesting channels to electrically isolate each anode panels and to be able to monitor the health of individual panel.

II. METHODS

A. San Diego Bay Deployments

Both Magic Carpet architectures were deployed in San Diego Bay adjacent to the Marine Corp Recruit Depot (32° 44' 20.65"N, 177 ° 12' 31.42"W) where Oregon State University, Naval Research Lab, and Spawar Systems Center-Pacific microbial fuel cells have been previously deployed and tested [12] (Fig. 1). The two architectures (Fig 2) were deployed Dec 2012 and March 2014 (respectively).

B. Materials Used in the Magic Carpet

The first system compared in this paper, Magic Carpet A (MCA), was deployed in San Diego Bay in December 2012 and was assembled of two parallel anodes constructed from two arrays of ten 1 m^2 panels of carbon fabric; buried at 12 cm and 24 cm. The individual $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$ carbon cloth panels for each anode were electrically connected via flat copper wire running the entire length as the main current collector. Two 16 gauge titanium wires were woven into each carbon cloth panel perpendicular to the copper wire as secondary current collectors. The electronics package for MCA consisted of a single channel energy harvester and power management system to which all of the BMFC electrodes were connected. Twenty 1.5 m carbon fiber bottle brushes were utilized as the cathode array. The carbon fabric BMFC anode and cathode (for MCB) were made from 16 gauge titanium wire (McMaster-Carr, Santa Fe Springs, CA) woven through $10 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$ carbon fabric cloth (Panex 30 PW-06; Zoltek Companies Inc, St Louis, MO). The carbon fabric cloth was sewn to the titanium wire to make a secure electrical connection. The end of the titanium wire was bent back on itself to prevent the carbon fabric and titanium wire from separating. Electrical connections were made from the titanium to copper wire (16AWG Marine Wire, Power Products, LLC, Menomonee Falls, WI) using a waterproof butt-splice (Power Products, LLC, Menomonee Falls, WI) that was sealed in a marine sealant (Marine Fast Cure 5200, 3M Corporation, St Paul, MN). The cathodes were suspended in the water column (Fig. 2A and 3). The cell potential of each BMFC was regulated to 400mV by a potentiostat board. This board controls the BMFC working potential to 400 mV and records power production data by using an electronics package constructed by Peter Kauffman (Northwest Metasystems, Seattle, WA) described earlier. Each anode was constructed from 10 carbon fabric with $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$ segmented panels. Each segment was electrically isolated with fiberglass screen to allow the overall system to act as 20 independent BMFCs. On each anode, five two-conductor insulated copper flat wire current collectors were run along the anode to contact the individual panels. Stainless steel staples were used to make a secure electrical connection between the carbon fabric and copper current collectors and then sealed with marine sealant. The copper flat wires were connected to an underwater cable and integrated into a load and monitoring system.

During sled deployment, the anodes were buried at depths of about 10 cm and 20 cm, respectively. The cathodes were suspended in the water column above the electronics pod (Fig.

2A and 3). The BMFC whole cell potential of the entire single channel system and the individual 20 channel system were regulated at $\sim 400 \text{ mV}$ using an electronic harvester that also converts the power to 12 V and records power production data to a logger (Northwest Metasystems, Seattle, WA; described earlier). In general, the potentiostat boards are designed to hold a system at a working potential equivalent to a reference set point (Ag/AgCL reference) designated before operation by tuning an onboard potentiometer.

C. Magic Carpet A

The first system compared in this paper, Magic Carpet A (MCA), was deployed in San Diego Bay in December 2012 and was assembled as two parallel anodes constructed from two sheets of ten segmented, 1 m^2 panels of carbon fabric; the upper 10 m anode buried at $\sim 10 \text{ cm}$ below the sediment surface and the lower 10 m anode buried at $\sim 20 \text{ cm}$. The electronics package for MCA consisted of a single channel energy harvester, boost converter and power management system to which all of the BMFC electrodes were connected. Twenty 1.5 m carbon bottle brushes were utilized as the cathode array.

D. Magic Carpet B

The second system, Magic Carpet B (MCB), was deployed in San Diego Bay in March 2014. The architecture differed in that the 10 individual $1 \text{ m} \times 1 \text{ m}$ carbon cloth panels operated as 20 independent BMFC anodes. These were connected to carbon cloth fabric cathodes in the water column (Fig. 2A and 3) via an external circuit. Each anode-cathode pair was connected to a similar energy harvester, boost converter and power management system as used for the single channel MCA. In addition, the current collectors in this system utilized copper flat wires routed to each sub-module and connected with sealed stainless steel staples.

Figure 1. Marine Corp Recruit Depot Test site in San Diego Bay .

Figure 2. A. Pictorial depicting the electronics schematic of the Magic Carpet BES. B. Basic design of the sled system and the magic carpet with two anodes (black anode buried at 10 cm and grey anode buried at 20 cm depths, respectively).

III. RESULTS

A. Magic Carpet A

Performance results for MCA (Fig. 4) showed that power increased during the first month following deployment reaching a maximum of about 260 mW in January 2013 and persisted until May 2013. This initial peak in power is consistent with previous observations that show highest power following initial installation when diffusion of organic matter to the anode is not limiting. Following May 2013, MCA power output showed a weak seasonal cycle between about 150-250 mW with highest levels during the late summer through fall and lowest levels during the winter and spring. Complete power loss was observed during low surface water oxygen events in the fall of 2013, however the system recovered from these events and power production resumed when oxygen levels normalized. Overall, MCA has averaged 197 mW of continuous power over the deployment period of 665 days, generating a total of about 3.1 kWh of energy.

Figure 3. Picture of Magic Carpet B with cloth cathodes contained in PVC pipe housing on top of sled mechanism.

B. Magic Carpet B

Results for MCB (Fig 5) were similar to MCA. Following deployment in March of 2014, power increased during the first month and stabilized at about 200 mW in April 2014. Diver observations during that time indicated that portions of the shallow anode were not well buried, so sediment was added manually in those areas. Power subsequently increased to about 280 mW by late May 2014. Based on this success additional manual burial was attempted, but this led to a rapid decrease in power to about 220 mW in early June of 2014. Following these interventions, MCB was left undisturbed and power was observed to increase to a maximum of about 250 mW in July 2014. Overall, the deep anode averaged about 74 mW and the shallow panel averaged about 133 mW for a system total of about 207 mW during the 225 day deployment period, generating a total of about 1.1 kWh of energy. Data collected from this unit indicated that the shallow anodes (buried at 12 cm) produced approximately twice as much power than the anodes buried at 24 cm. This was surprising as the deeper burial depth should result in more stable anaerobic conditions.

Figure 4. Twenty segmented BMFC, A; single channel. Performance results for MCA and temperature in San Diego Bay. Power production is shown on the Y axis versus time and the temperature is shown on the secondary Y axis.

Figure 5. Performance results for MCB showing the shallow, deep, and total power along with temperature. Power production is shown on the Y axis versus time and the temperature is shown on the secondary Y axis.

Figure 6. Cumulative energy comparison in watt-hours versus time in days for the 20 paneled BMFC. The top line represents a two year + timeline for the single channel BMFC, MCA. The following three lines represent the cumulative power for MCB and individual power for the lower (20 cm) and upper (10 cm) panels.

Figure 7. Variation of cumulative energy in watt-hours among the BMFC MCB panels. There were 20 panels; the lower panels buried at 20 cm and the upper panels at 10 cm. Panel 1 was closest to the electronics connection.

The system performance for MCA and MCB are similar when comparing cumulative energy production (Fig. 6). There seems to be no benefit to having individual channels. The initial goal of the individual channels was to isolate non-functioning anodes. In the past, were observed benthic animals (e.g. ghost shrimp) were seen to burrow near the electrodes, introducing oxygen to the anodic electrodes. This causes a collapse in the redox gradient and decrease in power production. In addition, both systems follow a similar pattern with an initial increased power production (after a lag phase of approximately 30 days). This has been observed in many experiments performed in this laboratory [6, 7, 10, 11, 12]. This is very likely due to depletion of organics in the sediment directly around the anodes. After organics have been depleted; anodic bacteria are dependent on fresh organic input from diffusion surrounding sediment [6]. Therefore, power production levels taper off to the diffusion limit, but do continue over long time-periods; as shown here; up to 2 years!

When analyzing the variation among the individual panels in the 20 segmented anodes, it is obvious that the upper panels (buried at 12 cm) out-performed the lower panels (buried at 24 cm). In most of these anodes, excepting panel pairs 4, 6, 8, and 9; power production was about twice that in the upper panels versus the lower panels (Fig. 7). This could be due to carbon form (labile versus refractory) in the upper 12 cm versus the lower 24 cm. It was assumed that the lower panels would out-perform the upper panels as there was less of a chance for burrowing or other oxygen inputs. However, this was not the case. Future studies will involve separating available carbon into labile and refractory pools. Also, every 3rd panel (panels 3, 6, and 9) seemed to provide higher power relative to other panels. This could be due to the wiring geometry; but this is unknown at this time.

IV. DISCUSSION

Together, these results indicate that large scale BMFC configured to be easily deployable in coastal waters can generate continuous power levels in the range of 200 mW and persist for years. Assuming a D-cell battery is approximately equivalent to 30 watt hours; both of these systems generate enough energy equivalent to 50 alkaline D-cell primary batteries per year. Also and important is the fact that these systems function over a long-time period.

Primary batteries would become exhausted over time and a sensor package would have to be sacrificed or retrieved to replace the batteries. Lastly, the ability of the BMFC systems to recover from environmental disturbances and produce power (e.g. following low oxygen events) shows the resilience of similar systems to provide long-term power for sensor networks.

Further investigations are underway to identify alternative approaches that can achieve target levels of 500-1000 mW for coastal BMFC systems. Due to power output requirements, optimizing numerous design considerations of BMFCs will be critical to powering a wider breadth of oceanographic instruments. However, at 200 mW, with persistence over multiple years, these systems are a viable seafloor power source for unattended sensors and systems.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This effort was funded by ONR grant # N0001414WX20018 and partially supported by the Navy Internal Science and Engineering 219 funds. The authors wish to thank Bradley Davidson who supported the field collection of sediments.

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